

D4.3. – Report on “Screening-and comparison of industrial crops grown on contaminated land”

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Executive summary

Contaminated land, that is unsuitable for food production, represents an alternative option for crops producing feedstock for bioproducts and bioenergy, which would otherwise be in competition with food production. It has been estimated that there are more than 10 million major contaminated sites worldwide, while in the European Economic Area (EEA)-39 countries the registered contaminated sites are up to 650000. Even though often perceived solely as a problem, contaminated areas could instead become a real asset that needs to be valued. One of the aims of MAGIC project was to screen the most promising industrial crops for cultivation on contaminated and saline soils. The effects of the heavy metals Cd, Pb, Ni and Zn on fifteen industrial crops were examined, namely on: biomass sorghum, camelina, cardoon, castor bean, crambe, Ethiopian mustard, giant reed, hemp, lupin, miscanthus x giganteus, pennycress, safflower, switchgrass, tall wheatgrass, and wild sugarcane (African fodder cane). The experiments were conducted following the same methodology and protocols by all partners involved. The levels of soil contaminations were: for Cd: 0, 4, 8 mg/kg, for Pb: 0, 450, 900 mg/kg, for Ni: 0, 110, 220 mg/kg and for Zn: 0, 450, 900 mg/kg. In addition, UNICT tested giant reed, miscanthus x giganteus and wild sugarcane under increased soil salinity levels. The 'crop X marginality factor' treatment was tested for two subsequent years, applying the completely randomized design in three replications. Growth and yield measurements, biomass characterization, as well as heavy metal determinations were analyzed in order to identify the most promising industrial crops to be cultivated in contaminated and saline soils. The results showed that zinc was the most toxic heavy metal, followed by nickel, cadmium and lead. None of the crops showed to be a hyperaccumulator of the tested heavy metals; however, some crops could accumulate in their aerial biomass metals in concentrations higher than the normal values, namely: (i) Cadmium concentrations were increased in sorghum > tall wheatgrass > castor \geq safflower > giant reed > Wild sugar cane > switchgrass > pennycress > Ethiopian mustard > miscanthus x giganteus, (ii) Increased lead contents were measured in pennycress > castor > hemp > crambe > safflower > lupin > Ethiopian mustard > switchgrass \geq sorghum > Tall wheatgrass > giant reed, (iii) increased nickel concentrations were observed in all crops, following the order: miscanthus x giganteus > castor > safflower > hemp > tall wheatgrass > pennycress > Wild sugar cane > giant reed > switchgrass > Ethiopian mustard > lupin > sorghum > crambe, (iv) zinc concentrations were within the normal limits for all crops, apart from hemp. Concerning camelina, the results differed between the four countries and could be grouped in terms of similarity into Greece & Italy and Portugal & Poland.

Concerning the salinity experiment the results are as follows:

In experiment 1, once giant reed plants were subjected to extreme salt stress a clear down regulation of ABA biosynthetic genes was registered suggesting that abscisic acid (ABA) synthesis might have a key role during the onset of stressful conditions as demonstrated in other species and in the case of water stress but not in the case of long-term stress. Another distinct trait of the giant reed response to extreme salt stress is the induction of clusters involved in brassinosteroid and protein IAA/AUX biosynthesis which probably have a key role in those more unfavorable conditions. Similarly, the down-regulation of gene involved in jasmonic acid (JA) biosynthesis suggests that JA signaling, leading to root growth inhibition, is repressed likely in the attempt to let the roots explore the surrounding soil more efficiently.

Furthermore, a dramatic change from C3 Calvin cycle to C4 photosynthesis is likely to occur when plants are exposed to extreme salt stress, as all gene regulation is addressed to repress Rubisco synthesis and assembly, and to activate the primary CO₂ fixation to PEP in mesophyll cells (C4 pathway). Considered the distinct response to salt dose, either genes involved in severe or in extreme salt response could constitute useful markers of the physiological status of giant reed in salinized soil.

The experiment 2 highlighted the high tolerance to salinity of the investigated perennial grasses, as the salinity levels employed were, respectively 2.8-fold (S1) and 5.6-fold (S2) higher than the threshold of 3.2 dS/m set in JRC report. Biomass yield was higher in giant reed and wild sugarcane than for miscanthus x giganteus. Salinity followed a gradient, decreasing as the salinity level increased: the biomass production between the salinity control (S0) and the medium salinity level (S1), across fertilizations, reduced by 21% in giant reed, 59% in wild sugarcane and 63% in miscanthus x giganteus. The reduction between S0 and the highest salinity level (S2) was 38% in giant reed, 60% in wild sugarcane and 70% in miscanthus x giganteus. Fertilization had a beneficial effect in the different salinity levels and crops. As expected, the highest fertilization clearly improved the biomass production in all crops under not saline environments. In a salinity of 9 dS/m (S1), the highest fertilization (F2) improved biomass production in giant reed by 25% and 42%, by 6% and 31% in wild sugarcane and by 49% and 93% in miscanthus x giganteus as compared with the F1 and F0, respectively. Under a salinity of 18 dS/m (S2), the F2 improved by 33% and 36% the biomass production in giant reed and by 53% and 94% in miscanthus x giganteus as compared with F1 and F0. The trend was not clear for wild sugarcane, which showed an increase of 1.7% between F2 and F0, but a decrease of 29% in F2 as compared with F1. Further work is necessary to confirm these results in different type of soil, and, most importantly using agamic material for propagation as much homogeneous as possible, as for example node cuttings instead of the presently used rhizomes, which are highly variable in size and bud number.

A. PHYTOREMEDIATION POT EXPERIMENTS

Partners:

AUA / Greece

UNICT / Italy

FCT UNL / Portugal

IWNiRZ / Poland

1. Introduction

1.1. Context and objective

In Europe, there are about 4.2 potentially contaminated sites (i.e. sites where unacceptable soil contamination is suspected but not verified) per 1,000 inhabitants and about 5.7 contaminated sites per 10,000 inhabitants (Van Liedekerke et al., 2014). Considering the whole Europe, this will result in an estimate of 2.5 million potentially contaminated sites, of which about 14 % (approx. 650,000) are registered contaminated sites and in need of remediation measures (Panagos et al., 2013; Mench et al., 2018).

Phytoremediation is the non-invasive technology of using green plants to remove contaminants from the environment or to render them harmless (Chaney et al., 1997; Gerhard et al., 2017). A new and more recent aspect of phytoremediation is **phytomanagement** in which remediation strategies are combined with sustainable and profitable site management options, resulting in a net gain in soil functions and ecosystem services, while producing economic revenue (Evangelou et al., 2015). In order to ensure sustainable phytomanagement applications, suitable fast growing, high biomass-yielding and value-added non-food crops are needed that can be used as feedstock for a wide range of products with different applications on industrial scale (e.g. biomaterials, bio-lubricants, bioplastics, pulp for paper, biochemicals, biofuels, biochar, etc).

Under the frame of MAGIC project, the **Sub-task 4.3.2** has been implemented in order to test the phytomanagement potential of the top 20 -finally selected by the project- most promising non-food crops to be cultivated in marginal lands. From these crops the trees has been excluded.

1.2. Crop selection

According to deliverable 1.3 and following the multi-criteria analysis, twenty crops were selected as most promising for cultivation in marginal lands (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Top 20 industrial crops that have been selected as the most promising to be grown on marginal lands facing natural constraints.

From these crops the woody species were excluded from the phytoremediation tests due to their growth (size and rate). In total 15 crops (Table 1) were investigated for their tolerance and accumulation potential in the heavy metals cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb) and zinc (Zn).

Table 1. Industrial crops investigated for their phytoremediation/phytomanagement potential.

a/a	Common name	Scientific name	Family	Life cycle	Category
1	Biomass sorghum	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (L.) Moench	Poaceae	Annual	Carbohydrate, Lignocellulosic
2	Camelina	<i>Camelina sativa</i> L.	Brassicaceae	Annual	Oil
3	Cardoon	<i>Cynara cardunculus</i> L.	Asteraceae	Perennial	Oilseed, Lignocellulosic Multipurpose
4	Castor bean	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Annual	Oil
5	Crambe	<i>Crambe abyssinica</i> L.	Brassicaceae	Annual	Oil
6	Ethiopian mustard	<i>Brassica carinata</i> A. Braun	Brassicaceae	Annual	Oil
7	Giant reed	<i>Arundo donax</i> L.	Poaceae	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
8	Hemp	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Cannabinaceae	Annual	Oilseed, Fiber, Multipurpose
9	Lupin	<i>Lupinus mutabilis</i> Sweet	Fabaceae	Perennial	Oilseed, Multipurpose
10	Miscanthus x giganteus	Miscanthus x giganteus J.M.Greef , Deuter ex Hodk., Renvoize	Poaceae	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
11	Pennycress	<i>Thlaspi arvense</i> L.	Brassicaceae	Annual	Oil
12	Safflower	<i>Carthamus dictorius</i> L.	Asteraceae	Annual	Oil
13	Switchgrass	<i>Panicum virgatum</i> L.	Poaceae	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
14	Tall wheatgrass	<i>Thinopyrum ponticum</i> (Podp.) Z.-W.Liu & R.-C.Wang	Poaceae	Perennial	Lignocellulosic
15	Wild sugarcane (African fodder cane)	<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i> L.	Poaceae	Perennial	Lignocellulosic

1.3. Contaminant selection

Soil pollution with organic and inorganic pollutants is becoming an increasingly severe environmental problem. It has been estimated that in the past half century, the global environment have received more than 0.03 million tons of Cr and 0.8 million tons of Pb that have mainly accumulated in soil and led to serious heavy metal pollution (Yang et al., 2018).

In Europe, the most frequent contaminants of soil are heavy metals and metalloids, affecting 35% of European soils (European Commission, 2013; Van Liedekerke et al., 2014). These elements arise in the environment from various sources, such as industry, mining, smelting, agriculture, transport, wastes, and fossil fuels combustion.

Among the heavy metals **Cd, Ni, Pb and Zn** are considered very important due to their wide spread and their negative impacts on the ecosystem and human health (Papazoglou, 2011; Briffa et al., 2020; Suhani et al., 2021) and with these heavy metals it was decided to work with in the pot experiment.

2. Methodology

In Month 7 of the project implementation all the protocols and the detailed methodology were decided. The same methodology/protocols were followed by all partners so as to compare the results among the tested plant species and to identify the most promising ones. Pot experiments were held for two consecutive years (2019 and 2020), applying the completely randomized design in three replications.

Typical agricultural soil of each country was artificially contaminated with nitric salts of Cd, Pb, Zn and Ni so as to achieve two different and relatively low contamination levels, close to the contamination of agricultural lands (Table 2). Control pots were also used and the contamination was applied two months before sowing the seeds in order for the metals to equilibrate in the soil fractions.

Table 2. Heavy metal concentrations in pot soils (mg/kg).

TREATMENTS	Cadmium	Lead	Nickel	Zinc
Control (mg/kg)	0 (Cd ₀)	0 (Pb ₀)	0 (Ni ₀)	0 (Zn ₀)
Low (mg/kg)	4 (Cd ₄)	450 (Pb ₄₅₀)	110 (Ni ₁₁₀)	450 (Zn ₄₅₀)
High (mg/kg)	8 (Cd ₈)	900 (Pb ₉₀₀)	220 (Ni ₂₂₀)	900 (Zn ₉₀₀)

The crop allocation per partner is shown in Table 3 and Figure 2. It was decided to use camelina as common crop along all partners for comparison reasons.

Table 3. Crop allocation per partner.

AUA, Greece	INICT, Italy	FCT UNL, Portugal	IWNiRZ, Poland
Camelina	Camelina	Camelina	Camelina
Sorghum	Giant reed	Crambe	Hemp
Castor	Wild sugarcane	Ethiopian mustard	Pennycress
Switchgrass	Tall wheatgrass	Miscanthus x giganteus	Lupin
	Safflower	Cardoon	

At the end of each growing period all plants were harvested and their growth was measured in terms of stem height and dry weight. In addition, the quality of the produced biomass was determined and the bio-accumulation potential of each crop was assessed by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy.

Figure 2. Photographs from the pot experiments per country.

3. Results

3.1. Impact of heavy metals to crop growth

At the end each growing period the plant height and the dry biomass production of each crop were measured. In Tables 4 and 5 the average values of the plant height per year are presented. The calculation of the average height values per crop for both years shows the following (the % shown below are results of the comparison between control and high treatments):

Biomass sorghum: The highest height reduction was observed in Zn treatment (60.5% for Zn₉₀₀), followed by Pb (25.7%) and Cd (9.2%). In Ni treatment a small increase was observed (1.8%).

Table 4. Plant height as affected by the heavy metals Cd, Pb, Ni, Zn in the first year (2019).

a/a	Crop	Height (cm) 2019											
		Cd ₀	Cd ₄	Cd ₈	Pb ₀	Pb ₄₅₀	Pb ₉₀₀	Ni ₀	Ni ₁₁₀	Ni ₂₂₀	Zn ₀	Zn ₄₅₀	Zn ₉₀₀
1	Biomass sorghum	239.1	262.8	177.4	235.4	232.6	176.7	247.4	200.4	276.0	225.4	196.3	0.0
2	Camelina - AUA	29.7	21.6	23.6	30.6	31.7	30.9	27.3	26.7	29.1	26.0	25.4	26.7
	Camelina UNICT	26.0	33.4	22.0	26.0	22.8	23.9	26.0	25.3	22.8	26.0	27.0	23.3
	Camelina FCT UNL*	63.1	52.2	46.2	63.1	65.5	58.3	63.1	60.4	52.0	63.1	58.3	54.9
	Camelina IWNiRZ	71.0	78.0	75.0	71.0	73.0	67.0	71.0	50.0	70.0	71.0	0.0	0.0
3	Cardoon**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	Castor bean	66.1	69.5	65.8	62.8	73.9	83.5	59.7	69.9	76.4	68.6	73.5	0.0
5	Crambe	60.0	45.7	47.4	60.0	58.0	58.5	60.0	55.1	46.2	60.0	62.9	57.7
6	Ethiopian mustard	110.0	117.3	94.3	110.0	67.6	73.3	110.0	69.3	64.4	110.0	77.0	84.2
7	Giant reed	58.7	53.8	74.1	58.7	67.8	77.3	58.7	53.0	46.4	58.7	60.6	60.2
8	Hemp	112.0	111.0	119.0	112.0	124.0	123.0	112.0	51.0	0.0	112.0	0.0	0.0
9	Lupin	87.0	90.0	91.0	87.0	91.0	74.0	87.0	44.0	0.0	87.0	0.0	0.0
10	Miscanthus x giganteus	99.7	79.2	106.7	99.7	120.9	107.5	99.7	133.3	32.5	99.7	83.7	115.3
11	Pennycress	5.0	6.0	5.0	5.0	8.0	6.0	5.0	7.0	5.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
12	Safflower												
13	Switchgrass	109.3	117.3	135.6	100.1	118.2	110.6	128.7	139.0	126.3	95.7	95.2	0
14	Tall wheatgrass												
15	Wild sugarcane	116.2	110.0	96.00	116.2	113.3	90.9	116.2	-	106.0	116.2	94.3	98.6

* as winter crop, ** seeds did not germinate

Camelina: In all partner countries camelina was sown as spring crop. During the first year (2019), in all the pot experiments the plants reached the seed phase very quickly probably due to unusually increased temperatures. All plants were dried, even the control ones. In the second year 2020, the seeds were sown earlier and the development of all crops was successful. Concerning the height, it is obvious that in the southern and warmer counties Greece and Italy the plant height is smaller than in Portugal and Poland. Generally, Cd and Pb did not affect significantly the plant height. For Ni treatments the results were controversial, namely in Greece, Portugal and Poland there was a significant reduction of 45.9%, 22.1% and 50.4% respectively, while in Italy there was an increase of 19.9%. The reductions of plant heights affected by Zn in Greece and Portugal were 19.6% and 25.2% respectively, while an increase of 19.9% was observed in Italy. In Poland, Zn treatment was lethal for plants.

Cardoon: the seeds did not germinate during both years, apparently due to bad quality.

Table 5. Plant height as affected by the heavy metals Cd, Pb, Ni, Zn in the second year (2020).

a/a	Crop	Height (cm) 2019											
		Cd ₀	Cd ₄	Cd ₈	Pb ₀	Pb ₄₅₀	Pb ₉₀₀	Ni ₀	Ni ₁₁₀	Ni ₂₂₀	Zn ₀	Zn ₄₅₀	Zn ₉₀₀
1	Biomass sorghum	239.1	262.8	177.4	235.4	232.6	176.7	247.4	200.4	276.0	225.4	196.3	0.0
2	Camelina - AUA	29.7	21.6	23.6	30.6	31.7	30.9	27.3	26.7	29.1	26.0	25.4	26.7
	Camelina UNICT	26.0	33.4	22.0	26.0	22.8	23.9	26.0	25.3	22.8	26.0	27.0	23.3
	Camelina FCT UNL*	63.1	52.2	46.2	63.1	65.5	58.3	63.1	60.4	52.0	63.1	58.3	54.9
	Camelina IWNiRZ	71.0	78.0	75.0	71.0	73.0	67.0	71.0	50.0	70.0	71.0	0.0	0.0
3	Cardoon**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	Castor bean	66.1	69.5	65.8	62.8	73.9	83.5	59.7	69.9	76.4	68.6	73.5	0.0
5	Crambe	60.0	45.7	47.4	60.0	58.0	58.5	60.0	55.1	46.2	60.0	62.9	57.7
6	Ethiopian mustard	110.0	117.3	94.3	110.0	67.6	73.3	110.0	69.3	64.4	110.0	77.0	84.2
7	Giant reed	58.7	53.8	74.1	58.7	67.8	77.3	58.7	53.0	46.4	58.7	60.6	60.2
8	Hemp	112.0	111.0	119.0	112.0	124.0	123.0	112.0	51.0	0.0	112.0	0.0	0.0
9	Lupin	87.0	90.0	91.0	87.0	91.0	74.0	87.0	44.0	0.0	87.0	0.0	0.0
10	Miscanthus x giganteus	99.7	79.2	106.7	99.7	120.9	107.5	99.7	133.3	32.5	99.7	83.7	115.3
11	Pennycress	5.0	6.0	5.0	5.0	8.0	6.0	5.0	7.0	5.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
12	Safflower												
13	Switchgrass	109.3	117.3	135.6	100.1	118.2	110.6	128.7	139.0	126.3	95.7	95.2	0
14	Tall wheatgrass												
15	Wild sugarcane	116.2	110.0	96.00	116.2	113.3	90.9	116.2	-	106.0	116.2	94.3	98.6

* as winter crop, ** seeds did not germinate

Castor bean: the plant height was not affected by Cd addition in the soil. An increase was determined under Pb and Ni treatments, i.e. by 18.3% and 14.7% respectively. The highest negative impact was observed in Zn₉₀₀ treatment, since in 2019 the seedlings were unable to grow and were dried.

Crambe: a reduction of 17.3% and 18.0% in Cd and Ni treatments was observed, while under the impact of Pb and Zn the plants were not significantly affected.

Ethiopian mustard: The plants were negatively affected by all metals. A reduction of 12.3%, 19.6%, 36.6% and 36.3% was determined under the high treatments of Cd, Pb, Ni and Zn respectively.

Giant reed: the addition of Cd and Pb resulted in an increase of height by 9.9% and 17.8% respectively. A reduction of 10.6% and 3.2% was measured under Ni Zn treatments.

Hemp: plant height was increased by Cd and Pb addition to the soil (10.2% and 16.4%), while high Ni and Zn treatment were lethal to all plants for both years. In 2019, the Zn₄₅₀ was lethal too.

Lupin: under Cd treatment the plant height was increased by 6.8%, while a reduction of 8.0% was determined under Pb treatment. In 2019, Ni₂₂₀ was lethal to all plants, while in 2020 a reduction of 33.8% was observed. In both years, both levels of Zn soil concentration were lethal to lupin plants.

Miscanthus x giganteus: Cadmium slightly reduce plant height (6.5%), while Pb and Zn slightly increase the height (3.8% and 6.6%). The most negative effect was observed in Ni treatment that significantly reduce the height by 56.2%.

Pennycress: under Cd, Pb and Ni treatment the height was increased by 19.1%, 34.8% and 1.7% respectively. The presence of Zn in the soil was lethal to all plants for both years.

Safflower: Due to late sowing and the consequent small size of the plants the harvest was not possible in 2019.

Switchgrass: plant height was increased by Cd and Pb by 10.0% and 2.2% respectively. A reduction of height was observed under Ni treatment (13.9%). The low Zn treatment did not affect the plants, while high Zn in soil was lethal to all plants for both years.

Tall wheatgrass: In order to ensure a good establishment, the first harvest was deferred to 2020.

Wild sugarcane: the height of this crop was reduced by 16.3%, 22.0% and 18.6% the high Cd, Pb and Zn treatments, while it was slightly increased by Ni (3.4%).

3.2. Crop tolerance per heavy metal.

Taking under consideration the germination percentage of the seeds (data not shown) and the growth of all plants the tolerance of each crop to each heavy metal has been estimated and is shown in the Tables 6 and 7. The symbol + represent a pot with well growing plant while the symbol – shows the pots with plants that either did not germinated at all or germinated but died later during vegetation. The percentages shown in the tables 6 and 7 represent the increase or decrease of the produced dry biomass per pot.

A **tolerance scale** is used in order to present the tolerance ability of the tested crops to Cd, Ni, Zn, and Pb and to facilitate their evaluation in terms of their sensitivity to these heavy metals. When differences -when compared to control- in the produced biomass (dry weight) represent a decrease up to 25% or an increase it is considered that the metal has little or no influence on plant productivity, classifying its tolerance as high. A decrease between 25% and 50% indicates that the presence of the contaminant in the soil moderately affects plant productivity. For yields decrease between 50% and 75%, the presence of the contaminant in the soil has a high effect on plant productivity, classifying its tolerance as low. A reduction in the yield higher than 75% indicates that the tolerance to this metal and level is critical, since virtually the entire culture has been lost.

The results presented in Tables 6 and 7 shows that the most toxic heavy metal is zinc since its high soil concentration was lethal -at least for one year- to eight crops, namely to: biomass sorghum, camelina, castor bean, hemp, lupin, pennycress, switchgrass and tall wheatgrass. Also the low Zn treatment (Zn_{450}) was lethal to four crops, namely to: camelina, hemp, lupin, and pennycress. Second on the row of toxicity is nickel, as in its Ni_{220} treatment all crops were dried or did not germinate at all in four crops: camelina, hemp, lupin, and pennycress. Cadmium is the third less toxic element: the highest concentration reduced the yield of camelina, and in particular in Italy for one year (2020). Low tolerance was also observed in tall wheatgrass and moderate tolerance was record in giant reed, miscanthus x giganteus, castor bean, crambe and camelina. In Cd_4 the crops Ethiopian mustard and tall wheatgrass showed low tolerance. Finally lead was the less toxic element since it was not lethal to any of the tested crops. In addition, its high soil concentration reduce the yield of only three crops by 50%-75%, i.e. of Ethiopian mustard, giant reed and tall wheatgrass.

To scale up the tolerance ability of each crop to the tested heavy metals the results of tables 6 and 7 were used (Figure 3). With red color are marked the crops that at least one year they were not affected by anyone of the tested metals. For tall wheatgrass in order to ensure plants become well established, the harvest was deferred on 2020. The major sensitivity of the wild sugarcane in 2019 compared to the 2020 is due to the small size of the rhizomes used in the first year.

Figure 3. Order of tolerance of each crop to the tested heavy metals Cd, Pb, Ni and Zn (i.e. high >less tolerance). With red color are marked the crops that at least one year they were not affected by anyone of the tested metals.

Table 6. Results of year 2019 of the pots with successfully grown plants (+), pots with plants that either did not germinated at all or germinated but died later during vegetation (-) and differences (%) in the produced dry biomass.

a/a	Crop	2019								
		Cd ₄	Cd ₈	Pb ₄₅₀	Pb ₉₀₀	Ni ₁₁₀	Ni ₂₂₀	Zn ₄₅₀	Zn ₉₀₀	
1	Biomass sorghum	+++ (+16%)	+++ (+12%)	+++ (-4%)	+++ (-29)	+++ (+10%)	+ - - (-60%)	+ + - (-20%)	- - - (-100%)	
2	Camelina AUA	Due to late sowing and unexpected high temperatures all crops (including the control ones) matured quickly and the yield comparison was not possible								
	Camelina UNICT	+++ (-15%)	+++ (-37%)	+++ (-12%)	+++ (+7)	+++ (+11%)	- ++ (-13%)	+++ (-20%)	- + - (-31%)	
	Camelina FCT UNL*	++ - (-22%)	++ - (-39%)	+++ (+19%)	+++ (+11%)	+++ (+5%)	+++ (-11%)	+++ (+11%)	+++ (+3%)	
	Camelina IWNiRZ	+++ (-5%)	+++ (-4%)	+++ (+12%)	+++ (-5%)	+++ (-92%)	- - - (-100%)	- + - (-100%)	- - - (-100%)	
3	Cardoon**	Seeds did not germinate								
4	Castor bean	+++ (-34%)	+++ (-44%)	+++ (+29%)	+++ (+2 %)	+++ (-11%)	++ - (-48%)	+ + - (-9%)	- - - (-100%)	
5	Crambe	+++ (-40%)	+++ (-37%)	+++ (-4%)	+++ (+27%)	+++ (-17%)	+++ (-23%)	+++ (0%)	+++ (+12%)	
6	Ethiopian mustard	+++ (-4%)	+++ (-9%)	+++ (-7%)	+++ (-3%)	+++ (-11%)	+++ (-37%)	+++ (-22%)	+++ (-20%)	
7	Giant reed	+++ (-38%)	+++ (-50%)	+++ (-22%)	+ - - (-64%)	+++ (-31%)	+ - + (-5%)	+++ (-34%)	+ - - (-54%)	
8	Hemp	+++ (+6%)	+++ (+12%)	+++ (+53%)	+++ (+84%)	+++ (-65%)	- - - (-100)	+ - + (-91%)	- - - (-100%)	
9	Lupin	+++ (+29%)	+++ (+46%)	+++ (+27%)	+++ (-33%)	+++ (-90%)	++ - (-100%)	- - - (-100%)	- - - (-100%)	
10	Miscanthus giganteus x	+++ (-15%)	+++ (-24%)	+++ (-13%)	+++ (+12%)	+++ (-5%)	+++ (-3%)	+++ (-14%)	+++ (-5%)	
11	Pennycress	+++ (-22%)	+++ (+22%)	+++ (+100)	+++ (+194%)	+++ (+144%)	- ++ (-100%)	- - - (-100%)	- - - (-100%)	
12	Safflower	Due to late sowing and the consequent small size of the plants the harvest was not possible								
13	Switchgrass	+++ (+15%)	+++ (+10%)	+++ (+19%)	+++ (+2%)	+++ (-3%)	+++ (+9%)	+++ (+16%)	- - - (-100%)	
14	Tall wheatgrass	+++ (-54%)	- ++ (-80%)	+++ (-25%)	+++ (-66%)	+++ (-50%)	+++ (-69%)	+++ (-32%)	- - - (-100%)	
15	Wild sugarcane	++ - (-35%)	++ - (-66%)	+++ (-16%)	+ - + (-40%)	- - - (-100%)	- ++ (-41%)	+++ (+5%)	+ - + (-35%)	
	High tolerance (yield reduction up to 25%)									
	Moderate tolerance (yield reduction up to 25%-50%)									
	Low tolerance (yield reduction up to 50%-75%)									
	Critical tolerance (yield reduction higher than 75%)									

* as spring crop; ** seeds did not germinate

Table 7. Results of year 2020 of the pots with successfully grown plants (+), pots with plants that either did not germinated at all or germinated but died later during vegetation (-) and differences (%) in the produced dry biomass.

a/a	Crop	2020							
		Cd ₄	Cd ₈	Pb ₄₅₀	Pb ₉₀₀	Ni ₁₁₀	Ni ₂₂₀	Zn ₄₅₀	Zn ₉₀₀
1	Biomass sorghum	+++ (-27%)	+++ (-5%)	++ - (+40%)	+++ (-14%)	+++ (+5%)	+++ (-11%)	+++ (+15%)	+++ (-11%)
2	Camelina AUA	+++ (-7%)	+++ (-9%)	+++ (+1%)	+++ (-4%)	+++ (-6%)	--- (-100%)	+++ (-34%)	+++ (-77%)
	Camelina UNICT	+++ (-25%)	+++ (-75%)	+++ (-18%)	+++ (-16%)	+++ (-11%)	++ - (-47%)	+++ (-11%)	+ - - (-66%)
	Camelina FCT UNL*	+++ (-21%)	+++ (-49%)	+++ (-39%)	+++ (-31%)	+++ (-50%)	+++ (-54%)	+++ (-31%)	+++ (-48%)
	Camelina IWNiRZ	+++ (+43%)	+++ (+34%)	+++ (+7%)	+++ (-8%)	+++ (-43%)	--- (-100%)	- - - (-95%)	- - - (-100%)
3	Cardoon	Seeds did not germinate							
4	Castor bean	+++ (-8%)	+++ (-23%)	+++ (+10%)	+++ (+20%)	+++ (-17%)	+++ (-9%)	+++ (+44%)	+++ (+36%)
5	Crambe	+++ (-17%)	+++ (+11%)	+++ (-17%)	+++ (-19%)	+++ (-12%)	+++ (-23%)	+++ (-16%)	+++ (-13%)
6	Ethiopian mustard	+++ (-54%)	+++ (-31%)	+++ (-54%)	+++ (-51%)	+++ (-49%)	+++ (-68%)	+++ (-74%)	+++ (-59%)
7	Giant reed	+++ (-14%)	+++ (-32%)	+++ (-23%)	- ++ (-38%)	++ - (-38%)	+ - + (-46%)	+++ (-25%)	- + - (-58%)
8	Hemp	+++ (+2%)	+++ (+9%)	+++ (+39%)	+++ (+49%)	+++ (-4%)	--- (-100%)	- - + (-83%)	- - - (-100%)
9	Lupin	+++ (+13%)	+++ (+15%)	+++ (+22%)	+++ (-17%)	+++ (-5%)	++ - (-96%)	--- (-100%)	--- (-100%)
10	Miscanthus giganteus x	++ - (-19%)	++ - (-34%)	+++ (-3%)	+++ (+8%)	+++ (+3%)	++ - (-22%)	+++ (-20%)	++ - (-27%)
11	Pennycress	+++ (-19%)	+++ (+1%)	+++ (+20%)	+++ (+3%)	+++ (+16%)	- ++ (-52%)	--- (-100%)	--- (-100%)
12	Safflower	+++ (+1%)	+++ (-9%)	+++ (+21%)	+++ (+13%)	+++ (-21%)	+++ (-38%)	+++ (-68%)	+ + (-56%)
13	Switchgrass	+++ (+4%)	+++ (+7%)	+++ (-11%)	+++ (-14%)	+++ (-15%)	+++ (-15%)	+++ (-18%)	--- (-100%)
14	Tall wheatgrass	+++ (-25%)	- ++ (-59%)	+++ (-42%)	+++ (-27%)	+++ (-29%)	+++ (-42%)	+++ (-22%)	- ++ (-33%)
15	Wild sugarcane	+ - + (-2%)	- ++ (+15%)	+++ (+15%)	++ - (+3%)	+++ (-8%)	+++ (+15%)	+++ (-36%)	+ - + (-38%)

	High tolerance (yield reduction up to 25%)	
	Moderate tolerance (yield reduction up to 25%-50%)	
	Low tolerance (yield reduction up to 50%-75%)	
	Critical tolerance (yield reduction higher than 75%)	

* as spring crop; ** seeds did not germinate

3.3. Heavy metal concentration in plant tissues

The concentrations of the tested heavy metals Cd, Pb, Ni and Zn are presented in Figure 4. The results are summarized as follows:

Cadmium: Increased Cd concentrations, higher than normal values in plant tissues, were measured in 10 crops. The heavy metal concentration relation was: sorghum > tall wheatgrass > castor ≥ safflower > giant reed > Wild sugar cane > switchgrass > pennycress > Ethiopian mustard > miscanthus x giganteus. In hemp, lupin and crambe the concentrations were within the normal limits. Camelina gave controversial results: in Greece and Italy the concentrations were high, reaching the 45.0 mg/kg at AUA and 22.2 mg/kg at UNICT experiments. On the contrary, in Portugal and Poland the higher determined concentrations were 1.5 and 4.2 mg/kg respectively.

Lead: The metal concentrations in plant tissues of miscanthus x giganteus and Wild sugar cane were within the normal limits. Increased lead contents were measured in: pennycress > castor > hemp > crambe > safflower > lupin > Ethiopian mustard > switchgrass ≥ sorghum > Tall wheatgrass > giant reed. The concentrations of lead in camelina were higher than normal in all countries, ranging between 26.2 mg/kg in Poland and 62.7 mg/kg in Greece.

Nickel: Concentrations higher than normal values in plant tissues were observed in all crops, following the order: miscanthus x giganteus > castor > safflower > hemp > tall wheatgrass > pennycress > Wild sugar cane > giant reed > switchgrass > Ethiopian mustard > lupin > sorghum > crambe. The concentrations in camelina plants were higher than the normal in all countries, reaching the 43.1 mg/kg at UNICT/Italy, 19.0 mg/kg at AUA/Greece, 16.3 mg/kg at IWNiRZ/Poland and 1.5 at FCTUNL/Portugal.

Zinc: the concentrations were within the normal limits for all crops, apart from hemp that gave 495.9 mg/kg.

Figure 4. Heavy metal concentrations in the aerial biomass of the tested crops.

3.4. Biomass characterization

Within species and across all contaminant and concentrations, Wild sugarcane had a higher hemicellulose content, both on leaves and stems than Giant reed, higher cellulose, and ADL on stems. The ash content was higher on leaves than stems on both species. Giant reed had a higher ash and NDS content than Wild sugarcane, both on leaves and stems (Table 8 and 9).

In Giant reed the hemicellulose content was the highest on the control than contaminated samples on stems, while it was similar on the leaves. The cellulose content on Giant reed stems was the highest in Ni110, while in Pb900 on leaves. The ADL was the highest and similar between the control and the Cd4 on Giant reed stems, while it was the highest in Pb900 for the stems. The NDS was the highest in Ni220 and Pb450 for the Giant reed stems and in Zn900 for Giant reed leaves. The ash content was the highest in Zn900 for Giant reed stems and in Zn450 for the leaves.

In Wild sugarcane stems, hemicellulose increased as compared to the control in Zn900, while on the leaves the hemicellulose was the highest on the control. The cellulose in Wild sugarcane stems was the highest in Pb450 and Zn450, as well as the leaves had higher cellulose content in Pb450. The ADL on stems was the highest in Pb450 and in Zn450 on leaves. The NDS in Wild sugarcane stems was the highest on the control, while it was the highest on Cd4 for leaves. Finally, the ash content was the highest in Cd4 for Wild sugarcane stems and in the control, Cd8 and pb900 for the Wild sugarcane leaves.

Table 8. Results of qualitative characterization of stems of giant reed and wild sugarcane in the first year (2019).

Sample	Contaminant	Concentration	Hemicellulose (Stems)	Cellulose (Stems)	ADL (Stems)	NDS (Stems)	ASH (Stems)
Giant reed	CTRL	-	30.34	29.59	7.08	27.43	5.56
Giant reed	Cd	4	31.42	30.84	7.51	25.00	5.23
Giant reed	Cd	8	26.13	28.14	5.58	32.40	7.75
Giant reed	Ni	110	29.17	30.45	6.55	27.78	6.06
Giant reed	Ni	220	27.10	26.65	6.12	33.94	6.20
Giant reed	Pb	450	26.55	26.09	5.82	33.73	7.81
Giant reed	Pb	900	27.07	29.44	6.01	29.88	7.59
Giant reed	Zn	450	25.94	28.01	5.82	31.90	8.32
Giant reed	Zn	900	25.16	28.25	5.11	31.77	9.71
<i>Average</i>			27.65	28.61	6.18	30.43	7.14
Wild sugarcane	CTRL	-	27.46	32.22	5.13	27.19	8.00
Wild sugarcane	Cd	4	31.91	35.26	6.98	16.25	9.60
Wild sugarcane	Cd	8	33.88	37.74	10.79	15.57	2.02
Wild sugarcane	Ni	220	39.57	30.58	6.68	16.98	6.18
Wild sugarcane	Pb	450	36.51	38.38	11.29	12.27	1.55
Wild sugarcane	Pb	900	34.46	37.08	8.77	15.11	4.59
Wild sugarcane	Zn	450	33.27	38.39	9.31	13.39	5.64
Wild sugarcane	Zn	900	38.91	33.88	8.58	14.33	4.30
<i>Average</i>			34.50	35.44	8.44	16.39	5.23

Table 9. Results of qualitative characterization of leaves of giant reed and wild sugarcane in the first year (2019).

Sample	Contaminant	Concentration	Hemicellulose (Leaves)	Cellulose (Leaves)	ADL (Leaves)	NDS (Leaves)	ASH (Leaves)
Giant reed	CTRL	-	28.15	23.50	3.96	34.54	9.85
Giant reed	Cd	4	28.57	26.39	4.76	31.79	8.50
Giant reed	Cd	8	29.18	26.64	4.30	30.22	9.67
Giant reed	Ni	110	28.28	24.90	4.13	33.30	7.92
Giant reed	Ni	220	29.49	25.22	5.07	32.65	7.56
Giant reed	Pb	450	28.31	27.08	3.87	29.89	10.85
Giant reed	Pb	900	24.60	28.45	6.78	32.12	8.06
Giant reed	Zn	450	25.55	24.73	3.42	34.05	12.25
Giant reed	Zn	900	23.46	19.60	4.36	41.33	11.26
<i>Average</i>			27.29	25.17	4.52	33.32	9.55
Wild sugarcane	CTRL	-	30.35	35.10	4.92	20.27	9.36
Wild sugarcane	Cd	4	34.65	31.58	5.06	22.33	6.38
Wild sugarcane	Cd	8	31.94	35.01	5.48	18.27	9.30
Wild sugarcane	Ni	220	32.72	34.03	5.80	18.51	6.47
Wild sugarcane	Pb	450	28.07	36.45	5.88	20.99	8.62

Wild sugarcane	Pb	900	32.69	34.47	5.09	18.63	9.12
Wild sugarcane	Zn	450	29.72	34.27	7.72	19.68	8.61
Wild sugarcane	Zn	900	32.41	32.60	5.38	22.80	6.82
Average			31.57	34.19	5.67	20.18	8.08

3.5. Additional work

AUA has established a field experiment (0.6 ha) so as to determine the biomass yield of each crop under the pedo-climatic conditions of Greece. This will help to extrapolate the possible extraction of the metals under field conditions.

4. Conclusions

The crops tested at the pot experiment of Task 4.3.2 were evaluated by the WP1 of MAGIC project as among the most promising for cultivation in marginal lands. The growth and the tolerance ability of the crops were affected differently by Cd, Pb, Ni and Zn, even though the protocols used were the same for all partners. Generally, zinc was the most toxic heavy metal, followed by nickel, cadmium and lead. None of the crops showed to be a hyperaccumulator of the tested heavy metals; however, some crops could accumulate in their aerial biomass metals in concentrations higher than the normal values, namely: (i) Cadmium concentrations were increased in sorghum > tall wheatgrass > castor ≥ safflower > giant reed > Wild sugar cane > switchgrass > pennycress > Ethiopian mustard > miscanthus x giganteus, (ii) Increased lead contents were measured in pennycress > castor > hemp > crambe > safflower > lupin > Ethiopian mustard > switchgrass ≥ sorghum > Tall wheatgrass > giant reed, (iii) increased nickel concentrations were observed in all crops, following the order: miscanthus x giganteus > castor > safflower > hemp > tall wheatgrass > pennycress > Wild sugar cane > giant reed > switchgrass > Ethiopian mustard > lupin > sorghum > crambe, (iv) zinc concentrations were within the normal limits for all crops, apart from hemp. Concerning camelina, the results differed between the four countries and could be grouped in terms of similarity into Greece & Italy and Portugal & Poland. Smaller plant height and heavy metal concentrations in values higher than normal were observed in Greece & Italy. Also the plants tolerance ability was different among the countries even though the same camelina's variety and the same cultivation protocols were used for all partners. This could be attributed to the different climatic conditions and the different physicochemical characteristics of the used soils that played an antagonistic effect to the heavy metal impacts by activating the plants' antioxidant defense and innate immunity system.

The conclusions at a glance are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Tolerance of the tested crops to Cd, Ni, Pb and Zn and their bioaccumulation potential

5. References

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B. SALINITY POT EXPERIMENT

Partner: UNICT / Italy

1. Introduction

According to the description of the work, the salinity trial, which was planned for task 4.3.1 was not conducted on field due to not possibility to in-situ trial. Therefore, it was moved to task 4.3.2, where pots were arranged to investigate industrial crops under increasing soil salinity levels. In two subsequent growing seasons, two research lines were carried out to assess the tolerance of different *Arundo donax* clones in terms of genetic response (experiment 1), and mitigation strategies of salinity stress, employing one clone of *Arundo donax*, one clone of *Saccharum spontaneum* spp. *aegyptiacum*, and *Miscanthus x giganteus* by increasing levels of fertilization (experiment 2).

Soil salinization is a severe environmental stress, that limits the productivity of agricultural crops. Although the amount of salt affected land (about 9 Mha) is imprecisely known, its extent is sufficient to pose a threat to agriculture since most plants, and certainly most crop plants, will not grow at high salt concentrations. Only halophytes (by definition) grow in concentrations of sodium chloride (NaCl) higher than about 400 mM. Salinization could commonly occur to agricultural practices associated with irrigation, and nearly 50% of irrigated soils in the world are somewhat salt affected. Not only irrigation but also sea water incursions into rivers or aquifers present in coastal areas could be a source of salinization.

The Na⁺ toxicity of many crop plants is correlated with over accumulation of Na⁺ in the shoot (Munns, 2002). The Na⁺ is taken up from the soil by the plant root system and transported to the shoot in the transpiration stream (Munns and Tester, 2003). Shoot Na⁺ accumulation is the net result of distinct Na⁺ transport processes occurring in different organs and cell types (Munns and Tester, 2003), and each of these processes contributes to the salinity tolerance of a plant.

According to Munns (Munns and James, 2002) physiological plant responses to water stress and salt stress have much in common; however, the mechanisms are extremely complex and vary with plant species as well as with the degree and time of exposure to stress. Photosynthesis, together with cell growth, has been reported among the primary processes affected by salinity or water stress (Chaves et al., 2009). Decreases in the photosynthetic rate under both stresses may be directly associated with a decrease in CO₂ availability related to stomatal closure (Flexas et al., 2007), or be due to alterations of photosynthetic metabolism (Lawlor and Cornic, 2002). At the same time, greater control of transpiration water loss is achieved to reducing the leaf expansion rate, preventing dehydration (Liu and Stützel, 2002) and acting as the first step in the process of stress acclimatization (Chaves et al., 2009). Changes in plant morphological components have also been reported; for example, a decrease in the leaf area index.

Stress tolerance of a plant species is usually determined by the plant's genes and also by morphological, phenological, physiological and biochemical traits. Therefore, measurements of different genetic and physiological processes during the plant's response to stress provide important information about the mechanism of the plant that are intended to remove or to reduce the harmful effects of stress in the plant tissues. Understanding the salinity tolerance of crop plants will provide an important contribution to the maintenance of crop yields and for cropping marginal lands affected by salinity (Grzesiak et al., 2013).

2. Methodology

The present work consists of two independent experiments, named Experiment 1 and Experiment 2, both involving perennial bioenergy grasses under increasing soil salinity levels. Experiment 1 evaluated the molecular mechanism involved in *Arundo donax* L. (giant reed) response to salt stress, by

conducting the de novo sequencing, assembling and analyzing the giant reed leaf transcriptome subjected to two levels of long-term salt stress under pots conditions and open air growth. In Experiment 2, evaluated the potential of three selected perennial lignocellulosic crops to increasing salinity levels: as C3 the *Arundo donax* L., as C4 the hybrid *Miscanthus x giganteus* and the *Saccharum spontaneum* L. spp. *aegyptiacum* (Willd.). The fertilization with different doses of mineral nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium (NPK) fertilizer was used to ascertain a possible mitigation strategy to salinity stress.

Experiment 1

The experiment was conducted at the Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment (Di3A) of the University of Catania, initially using three different giant reed clones, namely G2, G18 and G20 ecotypes, originated from Caltagirone (Italy), (latitude 37°14', longitude 14°31'), Biancavilla (Italy) (latitude 37°38', longitude 14°52') and Capo D' Orlando (Italy) (latitude 38°08', longitude 14°43'), respectively, and collected at the Experimental farm of the University of Catania, located in South Italy (10 m a.s.l., 37°24'N, 15°03'E). The trial started on July 7th, 2017, by transplanting *A. donax* rhizomes into 25 L pots (40 cm diameter and 30 cm height) containing a sandy soil as substrate. For each ecotype, samples showing homogeneous rhizome weight and same bud number were used for transplanting. The individual rhizomes were then placed at 15 cm depth, one for each pot. The pots were arranged according to a randomized block factor scheme in three replicates. During the experiment, the irrigation was performed on a weekly basis, and until the first sprouts was visible, tap water (5 L per pot) has been used. Irrigation was carried out manually using a watering can, avoiding possible leaks by leaching. The first irrigation with saline water was carried out on August 3rd, 2017. Salt stress was imposed by adding different concentrations of NaCl to the irrigation water. In particular, S0 samples (no salt added), S3 (severe salt stress, 256.67 mM NaCl corresponding to 32 dS m⁻¹ electric conductivity, EC), S4 (extreme salt stress, 419.23 mM NaCl corresponding to 50 dS m⁻¹ EC). G2 ecotype under S3 and S4 salt levels was investigated for global transcriptomic analysis, whose details are reported in Sicilia et al. 2019 (<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12870-019-1964-y>).

Experiment 2

The following factors were studied in a split-plot experimental design with three replicates: species in three levels, salinity in three levels and fertilization in three levels ($n=81$) (Figure 1). The substrate was a clay soil ascribable to the order of Entisols (U.S. Soil Taxonomy) with an alkaline reaction. The salinity treatment, in three NaCl levels, was the same in both the Experiment 1 and 2: tap water for S₀, 9 dS m⁻¹ for S₁ and 18 dS m⁻¹ for S₂. At each irrigation NaCl has been added to 13,5 liter of tap water for a total amount of 121,5 g of NaCl for S₁ and 243 g of NaCl for S₂, and adjusted after checking the water EC at each irrigation. Irrigation was carried out twice a week only with tap water from the moment of transplanting of rhizomes into the pots up to the stem elongation phase. When the plants reached 4-5 leaves, the specific amount of NaCl was added to tap water only for S₁ and S₂.

The fertilization treatment, in three level of NPK 18-18-18, was the same for both Experiments 1 and 2: 0 kg ha⁻¹ for F0, 60 kg ha⁻¹ for F1 and 120 kg ha⁻¹ for F2. The amount of fertilizer indicated in the experimental plan was distributed before transplanting the rhizomes in each pot for 60 kg N ha⁻¹ and 60 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 60 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ as 18N–18P–18K fertilizer for F1 and 120 kg ha⁻¹ for F2, respectively. After the stem elongation stage, the calculated amount of 18N–18P–18K fertilizer only for F2 remaining quantity was applied.

The pots have been arranged in an open space at the Department Di3A of the University of Catania

(Italy).

Figure 1. Experimental layout in the salinity stress trial in the Exp. 2.

Fresh rhizomes have been weighed and selected with 2–3 main buds (**Figure 2**) than directly transplanted at 1 rhizome per pot, which size was 25 cm for inner diameter containing approximately 10 kg of clay soil collected from the Experimental farm (University of Catania).

Figure 2. Rhizomes selected in the Laboratory.

In order to reduce the heterogeneity at the beginning, before transplanting on May 2019, rhizomes were selected with a similar weight where it could be possible. The initial fresh weight of the rhizomes changed between species with values ranging from 115.1 g for the *Arundo donax* to 24.2 g for the *Miscanthus x giganteus* and 28.7 g for the *Saccharum spontaneum* spp. *aegyptiacum*.

Measurement of electrical conductivity (EC) on soil in the pots have been performed with GS3 Sensor ProCheck (Decagon Devices, Inc.). Soil EC was measured at the beginning of the treatment (T₀) and then every week from the start of treatment with tap water plus NaCl on the S₁ and S₂ treatment, and up to one month before the biomass harvest time.

The instrument (XS COND 6+ EUTEC Instruments) was first calibrated, then the salinity of the water at the source was measured and finally the dose of NaCl to be added was weighed (g) to obtain irrigation water with the desired EC level for the respective S₁ and S₂ levels of the experiment.

Morphological measurements like basal stems diameter (mm), number of green and dry leaves, number of stems, main stem height from the base up to last node (cm), number of stems, and non-destructive leaf area index (LAI) were measured fortnight. Non-destructive LAI was calculated according to the equation developed for maize:

$$LAI = (L \cdot W) \cdot A$$

Where L, W and A are leaf length, leaf maximum width and a constant (A = 0.73) respectively.

Physiological measurement like net photosynthesis (A, $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), stomatal conductance (gs, $\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), and transpiration rate (E, $\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) using a portable photosynthesis system (LICOR 6400 system, LI-COR Bioscience) was set on the third last fully expanded leaf using at the moment of maximum intensity of solar radiation, from 12:00 to 14:00, at a flow rate of 500 mL min⁻¹ and ambient CO₂ concentration. Measurements were carried out from the stem elongation phase and

up to biomass harvest. The instantaneous water use efficiency (iWUE, $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ H}_2\text{O}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) was thus calculated as net photosynthesis to the transpiration rate at each measurement time.

Biomass harvest took place after one month of salinity irrigation treatment, collecting both the aboveground and the belowground biomass. The measurement parameters were: fresh matter yield (leaves and stems), basal stems diameter (mm), total number of green and dry leaves, number of stems, main stem height from the base of the cut up to last node (cm) and leaf area index (LAI).

After drying sub-samples in a stove at the temperature of 65 °C up to constant weight, the weight of dry leaves and dry culms was detected (g). For the belowground biomass the following parameters were detected: weight of rhizomes (g), roots weight (g) and number of buds.

Oven-dried samples were ground through a 1-mm screen in an IKA mill (IKA-WERFE, GmbH & Co., KG, Staufenim Breisgau, Germany). Cellulose, hemicellulose, acid detergent lignin (ADL), proteins, lipids and ash were determined by a near-infrared spectrometer (NIR, SpectraStar™ 2500XL-R, Unity Scientific) provided with a tungsten halogen lamp as light source and a high performance ultra-cooled InGaAs extended range detector, according to Scordia et al., 2017.

Biomass yield data were subjected to the three-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) according to the experimental layout, with species, salinity and fertilization as fixed factors (CoStat, version 6.0). The leaf area index and the instantaneous WUE through the growing season were analysed by a three-way ANOVA using repeated measurements in time, where the growing season represents the within-factor, and the species, salinity and fertilization the between-factor (SPSS, PAWS Statistics 18). When data failed the Mauchly's sphericity test, the univariate results were adjusted by using the Greenhouse-Geisser Epsilon and the Huynh-Feldt Epsilon correction factors. When univariate results satisfied sphericity tests for within-subjects effects, the F-values and associated P-values for between-subjects effects were tested. Differences between means were evaluated for significance using the Student-Newman-Keuls (S.N.K.) test at 95% confidence level.

3. Results

Arundo donax G2, G18 and G20 morpho-biometric and physiological parameters were measured at sampling date after being subjected to two levels of prolonged salt stress imposition (S3, severe and S4, extreme), being both doses much higher than that used to define a soil area as "salinized" (EC 4 dS m^{-1}). Considering the average values of the three clones, we observed that both the leaf number per pot, the stem number and the main stem height per pot, were significantly reduced by salt stress, and this effect was more pronounced in correspondence of the S4 treated samples. Similarly, physiological parameters such as SPAD, leaf chlorophyll content, net photosynthesis and biomass yield per pot decreased especially under extreme salt stress conditions (S4) compared with untreated S0 samples (Figure 3). The ecotypes under investigation exhibited different phenotypes in response to salt treatments, although they reproduce asexually and, for this reason, they should have low levels of genetic diversity. In particular, the whole data analysis revealed that G20 clone did not growth under extreme salt stress conditions, suggesting that it is highly sensitive to high salt concentration. Although both G2 and G18 clone grew under severe (S3) and extreme (S4) salt stress conditions, G2 clone showed higher stem and leaf number per pot, and higher physiological parameters than those recorded in G18 clone in S4 conditions.

Figure 3. Morpho-biometric and physiological measurement of G2, G18 and G20 under S0, S3 and S4 salinity levels

Indeed, G2 clone produced considerable higher biomass yield than that reported in G18 clone in extreme salt stress conditions, in an environment in which likely none crops could have survived. Therefore, further transcriptomic analysis was conducted upon G2 clone subjected to severe and extreme salt stress. The picture of giant reed phenotype under salt stress is shown Figure 4, while full set of data are available in Sicilia et al. (2019) (<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12870-019-1964-y>).

Figure 4. *Arundo donax* G2 clone subjected to control (S0), severe and extreme salt stress (S3 and S4, respectively).

Experiment 2

The ANOVA showed a significant effect ($P \leq 0.05$) of species, time of measurement, salinity, and the interaction of species x salinity, salinity x fertilizer and species x salinity x fertilizer on the number of green leaves. Fertilization and the interaction of species x time of measurement and species x fertilization were not significant (Table 1).

Table 1. ANOVA for green leaves using repeated measures on time for main effects (species, salinity and fertilization) and interactions. Mean separation of main effects according to Tukey Method and 95.0% confidence level.

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	103.483	146.91	0.000
Time (T)	6	45.038	63.94	0.000
S x T	14	1.178	1.67	0.079
Salinity(SL)	2	202.340	287.26	0.000
Fertilier (F)	2	0.244	0.35	0.708
S x SL	4	69.431	98.57	0.000
S x F	4	1.703	2.42	0.051
SL x F	4	10.895	15.47	0.000
S x SL x F	8	7.711	10.95	0.000
Error	144	0.704		

The mean separation of main effects revealed a significant difference between species and between salinity, but not between fertilization treatments (Table 2). Irrespective of soil salinity and fertilization, the three species showed a decreasing trend as the growing seasons moved forward. In giant reed there were no differences in the control between fertilization treatments, as well as in the S_1 although the number of green leaves was lower than the control.

Surprisingly, in the S_2 , *Arundo* under F_2 had as much leaves as the control, however there was a clear effect of the fertilization which reduced the number of green leaves as it was reduced. In *Miscanthus* no differences were observed between fertilization treatment within soil salinity. The S_1 showed green leaves less than the S_0 and the S_2 treatments, which had a similar number of green leaves. *Saccharum* showed a lower number of green leaves as compared with the other species. The salinity effect proportionally reduced the number of green leaves as it was increased

Table 2. Mean separation of main effects for green leaves according to Tukey Method and 95.0% confidence level.

Species	Green leaves (n.)
Arundo	6.1a
Miscanthus	3.6c
Saccharum	5.3b
Salinity	
S0	6.9a
S1	4.7b
S2	3.4c
Fertilization	
F0	5.1a

F1	4.9a
F2	5.0a

As for the stem height (cm) the ANOVA showed a significant effect ($P \leq 0.05$) of main effects, as well as of the first and second order interactions (Table 3). The mean separation of main effects revealed a significant difference between species and between salinity, but not between fertilization treatments.

Table 3. ANOVA for stem height using repeated measures on time for main effects (species, salinity and fertilization) and interactions. Mean separation of main effects according to Tukey Method and 95.0% confidence level.

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	24147.4	502.36	0.000
Time (T)	6	1064.1	22.14	0.000
S x T	14	242.4	5.04	0.000
Salinity (SL)	2	35532.3	739.21	0.000
Fertilier (F)	2	469.6	9.77	0.000
S x SL	4	9002.9	187.30	0.000
S x F	4	280.0	5.82	0.000
SL x F	4	1838.8	38.25	0.000
S x SL x F	8	679.2	14.13	0.000
Error	144	48.1		

Across the average of treatment, investigated species showed an increasing trend as the growing seasons moved forward (Figure 5). *Miscanthus* was more responsive to salinity stress as it showed the shorter stem height overall. *Saccharum* was the highest under the S_0 , however under the salinity stress giant reed kept the highest stem height. A clear fertilization effect was observed only in giant reed under S_2 condition.

The ANOVA showed a significant effect of measurement time, species and salinity levels, but neither fertilization nor the first order interactions were statistically significant for the leaf area index (Table 4). The second order interaction was marginally significant per $P \leq 0.05$. The leaf area index (LAI) of the investigated species under salinity and fertilization treatments showed an upward trend followed by a decline as the growing seasons moved forward. *Miscanthus*, followed by *Saccharum* showed the lowest LAI overall, which strongly decreased as the salinity increased, particularly in *Miscanthus*. *Arundo*, on the other hand, seems to be less responsive to soil salinity, as the LAI showed a similar trend between salinity treatments. The fertilization did not show appreciable differences between species and salinity levels (Figure 6).

The ANOVA showed a significant effect of time of measurement, species, salinity and fertilization on instantaneous water use efficiency (iWUE). The species x salinity, salinity x fertilization and species x salinity x fertilization interactions were also significant (Table 5).

Figure 5. Plant height (cm) of *Arundo donax* (A-C), *Miscanthus x giganteus* (D-F) and *Saccharum spontaneum* (G-I) under different salinity levels (S0, S1, S2), and NPK fertilization (F0, F1, F2). Significant LSD interaction of “species x salinity x fertilization” at $P \leq 0.05$ (13.43).

Table 4. Repeated measure ANOVA for within (time) and between-subject effects (species, salinity, fertilization) (F) on leaf area index (LAI).

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	550.36	239.37	0.000
Time (T)	6	50.38	21.91	0.000
S x T	14	30.27	13.17	0.000
Salinity (SL)	2	10.45	4.55	0.012
Fertilization (F)	2	3.59	1.56	0.213
S x SL	4	4.85	2.11	0.082
S x F	4	2.84	1.23	0.299
SL x F	4	5.49	2.39	0.079
S x SL x F	8	9.53	4.15	0.058
Error	144	2.30		

Figure 6. Leaf area index of *Arundo donax* (A-C), *Miscanthus x giganteus* (D-F) and *Saccharum spontaneum* (G-I) under different salinity levels (S0, S1, S2), and NPK fertilization (F0, F1, F2). Significant LSD interaction of “species x salinity x fertilization” at $P \leq 0.05$ (2.05).

Table 5. Repeated measure ANOVA for within (time) and between-subject effects (species, salinity, fertilization) (F) on instantaneous water use efficiency (iWUE)

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	11.25	28.12	0.000
Time (T)	5	35.04	87.59	0.000
S x T	10	0.92	2.31	0.016
Salinity (SL)	2	9.95	24.87	0.000
Fertilier (F)	2	3.19	7.99	0.001
S x SL	4	18.46	46.15	0.000
S x F	4	0.71	1.78	0.138
SL x F	4	4.37	10.92	0.000
S x SL x F	8	4.09	10.23	0.000
Error	121	0.40		

The iWUE of the investigated species under salinity and fertilization treatments showed a fluctuating trend around the mean throughout the growing season (Figure 7). Although the different photosynthetic pathway (C3 for *Arundo* and C4 for both *Saccharum* and *Miscanthus*), the iWUE, which represents the net photosynthesis over the transpiration rate, was similar among species.

Figure 7. Instantaneous water use efficiency of *Arundo donax* (A-C), *Miscanthus x giganteus* (D-F) and *Saccharum spontaneum* (G-I) under different salinity levels (S0, S1, S2), and NPK fertilization (F0, F1, F2). Significant LSD interaction of species x salinity x fertilization at $P \leq 0.05$ (0.85).

The mean separation showed that *Miscanthus* and *Arundo* were significantly higher than *Saccharum* across salinity and fertilization, that S2 was significantly higher than S1 and S0 across species and fertilizations, and that F0 and F1 were significantly higher than F2 across species and salinity levels. Biomass production at harvest is the most important trait to evaluate crop performance under stressful conditions. The ANOVA showed a significant effect of fixed factors and the interaction of species x salinity (Table 6).

The other first order, as well as the second order interactions were not statistically significant.

Table 6. ANOVA for main effects and interactions on biomass production.

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	1704.2	69.61	0.000
Salinity (SL)	2	1461.6	59.71	0.000
Fertilier (F)	2	233.83	9.55	0.003
S x SL	4	166.47	6.80	0.002
S x F	4	26.77	1.09	0.369
SL x F	4	12.67	0.517	0.723
S x SL x F	8	45.99	1.87	0.083
Error	52	24.48		

Figure 8 showed that biomass production was the significantly highest in *Saccharum* S0-F2 (40.6 g plant⁻¹) and the significantly lowest in *Miscanthus* S1-F1, *Miscanthus* S2-F1, *Miscanthus* S1-F0 and

Miscanthus S2-F0 (averaged 2.54 g plant⁻¹). However, *Saccharum* S0-F1, *Arundo* S0-F1, *Saccharum* S0-F0, *Arundo* S0-F2 and *Arundo* S1-F2 were not statistically different than the highest yielding combination (averaged 29.35 g plant⁻¹).

The biomass production between the salinity control (S0) and the medium salinity level (S1), across fertilizations, reduced by 21% in *Arundo*, 59% in *Saccharum* and 63% in *Miscanthus*. The reduction between S0 and the highest salinity level (S2) was 38% in *Arundo*, 60% in *Saccharum* and 70% in *Miscanthus*. *Saccharum* between S1 and S2 reduced by only 0.5%, while *Arundo* and *Miscanthus* by 21% and 19%, respectively.

In the salinity control (S0), the highest fertilization (F2) improved the biomass production in *Saccharum* by 21% and 30% as compared with the medium (F1) and unfertilized treatment (F0). In *Arundo* and *Miscanthus* such improvement was observed only between F2 and F0 (18% and 2%, respectively), while between F2 and F1 a reduction was registered (-11% and -27% for *Arundo* and *Miscanthus*, respectively). In intermediate salinity level (S1), *Arundo* under F2 improved by 25% and 42% as compared with the F1 and F0. Such improvement was of 6% and 31% in *Saccharum* and 49% and 93% in *Miscanthus*. In the most stress salinity condition (S2), the F2 improved of 33% and 36% the biomass production of *Arundo* as compared with F1 and F0, of 53% and 94% in *Miscanthus*, and of 1.7% in *Saccharum* between F2 and F0. *Saccharum* reduced by 29% the biomass production of F2 as compared with F1 in S2.

Figure 8. Biomass yield (g plant⁻¹) in combination of experimental factors, namely species (*Arundo donax* - AD, *Miscanthus x giganteus* - MxG, *Saccharum spontaneum* - SSA), salinity levels (S0, S1, S2), and NPK fertilization (F0, F1, F2). Different letters indicate statistical significance according to the SNK test at P≤0.05.

The mean separation of the main factors showed a higher biomass production and not statistically different for *Arundo* and *Saccharum*, and the lowest for *Miscanthus*. Biomass dry weight was significantly highest in S0, followed by S1 and by S2, while among fertilization, the biomass dry weight was the highest in F2 and the lowest but not different in F1 and F0 (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Mean significance of species, salinity and fertilization main effects. Different letters indicate statistical significance according to the SNK test at $P \leq 0.05$.

The table 7 shows the ANOVA for hemicellulose content on leaves of perennial grasses under salinity and fertilization levels. The three main effects were highly significant, as well as the interactions, except the third order one.

Table 7. ANOVA for main effects and interactions on hemicellulose content on leaf.

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	176.14	371.85	0.000
Salinity (SL)	2	55.28	116.70	0.000
Fertilier (F)	2	2.94	6.22	0.004
S x SL	4	3.11	6.58	0.000
S x F	4	2.21	4.67	0.003
SL x F	4	1.16	3.41	0.015
S x SL x F	8	0.85	1.80	0.097
Error	54	0.47		

The mean separation of main effect showed that leaves of *Miscanthus* and *Saccharum* had a significantly higher hemicellulose content than *Arundo*. The soil salinity increase lead to a linear decrease of this component on leaves, while increasing the fertilization showed the opposite trend (Table 8). The hemicellulose content on stems was significant for the species and salinity main effect, while did not for the fertilization (Table 9). There were significant interactions, like species x fertilization, salinity x fertilization, and the species x salinity x fertilization. The mean separation of main effect showed a significantly higher hemicellulose content on the stems of *Arundo* and *Saccharum* and the lowest in *Miscanthus*. The salinity also in this case led to a decrease of this component on the stems, while the fertilization did not make substantial changes (Table 10).

Table 8. Mean separation of main effects for hemicellulose content on leaf according to Tukey Method and 95.0% confidence level.

Species	H_leaf
Arundo	28.92b
Miscanthus	33.47a
Saccharum	33.21a
Salinity	
S0	33.34a
S1	31.80b
S2	30.48c
Fertilization	
F0	31.49b
F1	32.07a
F2	32.05a

Table 9. ANOVA for main effects and interactions on hemicellulose content on stems.

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	94.27	313.22	0.000
Salinity (SL)	2	38.70	128.61	0.000
Fertilier (F)	2	0.261	0.87	0.426
S x SL	4	0.683	2.27	0.073
S x F	4	5.01	16.67	0.000
SL x F	4	3.20	10.64	0.000
S x SL x F	8	1.12	3.73	0.002
Error	54	0.30		

Table 10. Mean separation of main effects for hemicellulose content on stems according to Tukey Method and 95.0% confidence level.

Species	H_stem
Arundo	29.31a
Miscanthus	27.01b
Saccharum	29.15a
Salinity	
S0	29.34a
S1	28.18b
S2	26.94c
Fertilization	
F0	28.04a
F1	28.20a
F2	28.22a

The cellulose content on leaves was significant for only species and salinity (Table 11). The ANOVA, however, showed also a significant effect of salinity x fertilization interaction. Among species, *Saccharum* had the significantly highest content of cellulose on leaves, followed by *Miscanthus* and *Arundo* with the lowest. Increasing the salinity, decreased the cellulose content on leaves, while the fertilization had no effect (Table 12).

Table 11. ANOVA for main effects and interactions on cellulose content on leaves

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	215.06	412.19	0.000
Salinity (SL)	2	45.37	86.96	0.000
Fertilier (F)	2	0.24	0.47	0.629
S x SL	4	0.84	1.62	0.183
S x F	4	3.43	6.56	0.000
SL x F	4	0.241	0.46	0.763
S x SL x F	8	0.312	0.60	0.755
Error	54	0.522		

Table 12. Mean separation of main effects for cellulose content on leaves according to Tukey Method and 95.0% confidence level.

Species	C_leaf
Arundo	24.72c
Miscanthus	28.79b
Saccharum	30.14a
Salinity	
S0	29.20a
S1	27.83b
S2	26.61c
Fertilization	
F0	27.99a
F1	27.81a
F2	27.85a

Similarly, the ANOVA for the cellulose content on stems showed a significant effect of species, salinity and the interaction between these two main factors (Table 13).

Table 13. ANOVA for main effects and interactions on cellulose content on stems.

Source	DF	Adj MS	F	P
Species (S)	2	36.64	63.30	0.000
Salinity (SL)	2	10.69	18.48	0.000
Fertilier (F)	2	5.40	9.33	0.000
S x SL	4	0.19	0.34	0.847
S x F	4	2.29	3.96	0.007
SL x F	4	0.37	0.65	0.628
S x SL x F	8	0.56	0.97	0.466
Error	54	0.57		

Among species, *Arundo* showed the significantly highest cellulose content on stems, followed by *Miscanthus* and by *Saccharum*. Also in this case, increasing the salinity level decreased significantly the cellulose content on stems (Table 14).

Table 14. Mean separation of main effects for cellulose content on stems according to Tukey Method and 95.0% confidence level.

Species	C_stem
Arundo	31.43a
Miscanthus	30.35b
Saccharum	29.10c
Salinity	
S0	30.92a
S1	30.30b
S2	29.66c
Fertilization	
F0	30.73a
F1	30.32ab
F2	29.83b

The figure 10 and 11 show the interaction of the main factors on the biomass parameters analyzed on the leaves and stems of *Arundo*, *Miscanthus* and *Saccharum*. Hemicellulose content in *Arundo* was consistently distributed on stems and leaves, while both *Miscanthus* and *Saccharum* showed a higher hemicellulose content on the leaves than the stems (Figure 10). On the cellulose front, *Saccharum* had a similar content between stems and leaves, while *Arundo* had a higher content on stems than leaves and *Miscanthus* a higher content on leaves than stems (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Hemicellulose content on leaves (above) and stems (below) of *Arundo donax*, *Miscanthus x giganteus* and *Saccharum spontaneum* under different salinity levels (S0, S1, S2), and NPK fertilization (F0, F1, F2).

Figure 11. Cellulose content on leaves (above) and stems (below) of *Arundo donax*, *Miscanthus x giganteus* and *Saccharum spontaneum* under different salinity levels (S0, S1, S2), and NPK fertilization (F0, F1, F2).

5. Conclusions

Experiment 1

Leaf transcriptome in response to the above salt stresses showed that most of the *A. donax* annotated DEGs are homologs of genes belonging also to other species (*Setaria italica* and *Zea mays*) thus suggesting that long term salt stress regulates a specific set of genes providing a general overview of the prolonged salt stress transcriptional responses in *A. donax*. The picture that emerges from the identification of functional genes related to salt stress is consistent with a dose-dependent response to salt. The number of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) under extreme salt stress is much higher than that observed in severe salt stress suggesting that a deep re-programming of the gene expression must occur in S4 samples, which, during the experiment, certainly grew in an “emergency” state. As concerns hormone regulation, the response to S3 severe salt stress seems not to be dependent by ABA levels as gene involved in its biosynthesis are not differently regulated whereas the clusters encoding the main catabolic enzyme are strongly up-regulated. Moreover, once *A. donax* plants were subjected to S4 extreme salt stress a clear down regulation of ABA biosynthetic genes is registered suggesting that ABA synthesis might have a key role during the onset of stressful conditions as demonstrated in other species and in the case of water stress but not in the case of long term stress. Another distinct trait of the *A. donax* response to S4 extreme salt stress is the induction of clusters involved in brassinosteroid and IAA/AUX biosynthesis which probably have a key role in those more unfavorable conditions. Similarly, the down-regulation of gene involved in jasmonic acid (JA) biosynthesis suggests that JA signaling, leading to root growth inhibition, is repressed likely in the attempt to let the roots explore the surrounding soil more efficiently. The analysis of clusters related to ethylene biosynthesis and signaling indicated that, exclusively under S4 extreme salt stress, the gene transcription is modulated towards the minimization of ethylene negative effects upon plant growth. The *A. donax* leaves subjected to S3 severe salt stress respond to salt-induced oxidative stress by the induction of genes involved in ROS scavenging (APX) and in redistributing the reducing power excess among cell compartments (malate valve). Along with the clusters implicated in the malate valve, under S4 extreme salt stress, also gene encoding the alternative oxidase (AOX) have been found up regulated, highlighting once more that the induction of some pathways occurs in the case of more stringent environmental conditions. A clear involvement of proline and polyamines in coping the salt-induced osmotic stress can be suggested whereas sugars seem not to be involved as osmolytes protecting cell homeostasis. Certainly, the photosynthesis and photorespiration processes are strongly affected since under S3 severe salt treatment, genes involved in Rubisco assembly are down-regulated, and the fact that *A. donax* leaf are impeded to operate CO₂ fixation via C3 Calvin cycle is also supported by the up-regulation of genes involved in photorespiration (glycolate oxidase). Conversely, in S4 extreme salt treated samples, a dramatic change from C3 Calvin cycle to C4 photosynthesis is likely to occur as all gene regulation is addressed to repress Rubisco synthesis and assembly, and to activate the primary CO₂ fixation to PEP in mesophyll cells (C4 pathway), this probably being the main finding the present work. Considered the distinct response to salt dose, either genes involved in S3 severe or in S4 extreme salt response could constitute useful markers of the physiological status of *A. donax* in salinized soil. Moreover, many of the unigenes identified in the present study have the potential to be used for the development of novel *A. donax* varieties with improved productivity and stress tolerance, in particular

the knock out of the GTL1 gene acting as negative regulator of water use efficiency has been proposed as good target for genome editing experiments.

Experiment 2

Growing bioenergy crops on marginal lands might in part mitigate the land abandonment due to degradation and unproductivity, reduce the land use changes and provide the raw material for a bioeconomy development. However, crops with excellent adaption strategies to growing limiting conditions are necessary to produce sufficient and profitable biomass under certain environments dominated by biophysical constraints. The JRC study indicated that soils are classified affected by salinity if the topsoil electrical conductivity is equal or higher than 3.2 dS/m. The present study highlights the high tolerance to salinity of the investigated perennial grasses, as the salinity levels employed were, respectively 2.8-fold (S1) and 5.6-fold (S2) higher than the threshold of 3.2 dS/m.

While morphological and physiological traits throughout the experimental period were somewhat affected, there was a not clear trend with the treatments imposed to the crops, although main effects were statistically significant. On the other hand, biomass productivity at harvest is the most important trait to evaluate crop performance under stressful conditions. The mean separation of the main factors showed a higher biomass production for *Arundo* and *Saccharum* than for *Miscanthus*. Salinity followed a gradient, decreasing as the salinity level increased: the biomass production between the salinity control (S0) and the medium salinity level (S1), across fertilizations, reduced by 21% in *Arundo*, 59% in *Saccharum* and 63% in *Miscanthus*. The reduction between S0 and the highest salinity level (S2) was 38% in *Arundo*, 60% in *Saccharum* and 70% in *Miscanthus*. Fertilization had a beneficial effect in the different salinity levels and crops. As expected, the highest fertilization clearly improved the biomass production in all crops under not saline environments. In a salinity of 9 dS/m (S1), the highest fertilization (F2) improved biomass production in *Arundo* by 25% and 42%, by 6% and 31% in *Saccharum* and by 49% and 93% in *Miscanthus* as compared with the F1 and F0, respectively. Under a salinity of 18 dS/m (S2), the F2 improved by 33% and 36% the biomass production in *Arundo* and by 53% and 94% in *Miscanthus* as compared with F1 and F0. The trend was not clear for *Saccharum*, which showed an increase of 1.7% between F2 and F0, but a decrease of 29% in F2 as compared with F1. Further work is necessary to confirm these results in different type of soil, and, most importantly using agamic material for propagation as much homogeneous as possible, as for example node cuttings instead of the presently used rhizomes, which are highly variable in size and bud number.

6. References

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